

SLA-Driven Adaptive FL policy with Real-Time Visualization for Zero-Touch 6G Network Slicing

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Abstract—6G paradigm enables massive network slicing for pervasive digitization across vertical industries, demanding scalable, sustainable, AI-driven zero-touch automation, particularly under non-IID conditions in live networks. This work introduces a cloud-native service-level agreement (SLA)-driven stochastic policy to guarantee a scalable and fast operation of constrained federated learning (FL)-based analytic engines (AE) that perform statistical slice-level resource provisioning at RAN-Edge domain, deploying on the kubernetes platform with real-time visualization capability. The key novelty lies in an SLA-aware adaptive learning rate policy to tune the local model’s learning rate dynamically during FL local training to enhance stability and convergence. Besides, to sustain scalability under massive slicing, we leverages SLA-driven stochastic AE selection policy in each FL training round, maintaining computational efficiency while reducing computational overhead. Extensive experiments in both simulated and emulated environments demonstrate significant reductions in SLA violations, enhanced convergence stability, and improved scalability compared to conventional FL approaches.

Index Terms—6G, kubernetes, federated learning, game theory, proxy-Lagrangian, resource allocation, SLA, ZSM

I. INTRODUCTION

6G networks are envisioned to intelligently manage an enormous number of concurrent and diverse network slices, each serving distinct vertical applications. This introduces major challenges in terms of scalability and sustainability for AI-driven, zero-touch End-to-End (E2E) slices management and orchestration, especially under stringent Service Level Agreements (SLAs). To address such challenges, the ETSI Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM) framework has been introduced a reference architecture that leverages AI-based closed-loop automation [1]. However, traditional centralized approach faces several limitations such as excessive communication overhead, latency, and vulnerability to single points of failure. Conversely, decentralized paradigms particularly Federated Learning (FL) emerge as a promising solution to analyze dispersed data locally, improved scalability minimizing computation and communication costs while enabling rapid and privacy-preserving decision-making. However, under non-IID conditions, conventional FL algorithms like FedAvg

and its variants [2] suffer from client parameter drift, slower convergence, and reduced accuracy, as they fail to adapt or learn personalized models for each client [3]. To address these issues, prior works have focused on optimizing FL algorithms through strategies such as (i) adjusting local update frequencies, (ii) selective client participation, and (iii) adaptive weighting schemes [4], [5]. Despite progress, most methods still rely on static learning rates, which fail to adapt to the diversity in data distribution and computational capabilities across clients [6]. Static configurations often lead to suboptimal convergence behavior and inconsistent global model performance. Several studies have explored dynamic learning rate adaptations. For instance, the work of [7] derives learning rates based on aggregation frequency, while [8] proposes an adaptive strategy that jointly optimizes local epochs and learning rates using a proximal regularization term. However, most studies overlook theoretically grounded learning rate optimization to handle heterogeneity. Recently, [9] proposed FedEnt, an entropy-based adaptive FL framework that dynamically tunes learning rates for faster convergence and greater robustness under non-IID conditions.

In practice, FL systems must operate within these SLA-defined boundaries, which often include constraints on accuracy, convergence speed, energy efficiency, and responsiveness to dynamic network conditions. Recognizing this, our previous work [10] proposed a cloud-native SLA-driven stochastic FL policy with an adaptive client selection mechanism for enabling scalable and efficient slice-level resource prediction under non-IID conditions. However, the dynamic nature of federated environments, where clients exhibit diverse datasets, computing capabilities, and network conditions, demands a more adaptive and context-aware learning strategy. As emphasized in [11], aligning learning dynamics with SLA targets requires that the system continuously adapts its behavior, particularly its learning rate—based on real-time performance feedback. This motivates the need for a flexible FL framework that dynamically adjusts its training strategy according to SLA metrics, ensuring efficiency, compliance, and responsiveness

while leveraging our previously proposed SLA-driven client selection policy.

The main contributions are:

- We formulate the FL based resource provisioning task at the local analytic engines (AEs) as a corresponding SLA-constrained optimization problem under the proxy-Lagrangian framework and solve it via a non-zero sum two-player game strategy to ensure fairness and convergence.
- To ensure scalability under massive slicing, we incorporate our previously proposed SLA-driven stochastic FL policy [10] for selecting a subset of AEs that will participate in each FL round, which enhances the convergence time while maintaining the same computation cost, regardless the number of AEs increases.
- We propose a novel adaptive learning rate policy that dynamically adjusts the learning rate during FL training according to the SLA violation rates which improve convergence stability under non-IID data.
- Finally, We implement a Kubernetes-based FL system with real-time visualization for scalable orchestration, monitoring, and evaluation, thereby validating our proposed solution in the realistic cloud native environment.

II. PROPOSED NETWORK MODEL AND DATASETS

As shown in Fig.1, a 6G RAN-Edge topology under a per-slice central unit (CU)/distributed unit (DU) functional split, wherein each transmission/reception point (TRP) is co-located with its DUs has considered. Basically, each CU consists of a monitoring system (MS) and an AI-enabled slice resource allocation function called analytic engine (AE).

Each CU k ($k = 1, \dots, K$) runs as a virtual network function (VNF) on top of a commodity hardware, and performs slice level RAN key performance indicators data collection to build its local datasets for slice n ($n = 1, \dots, n$), i.e., $\mathcal{D}_{k,n} = \{\mathbf{x}_{k,n}^{(i)}, y_{k,n}^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^{D_{k,n}}$, where $\mathbf{x}_{k,n}^{(i)}$ stands for the input features vector while $y_{k,n}^{(i)}$ represents the corresponding output.

Figure 1: Proposed architecture

Assumed that the collected datasets are generally non-exhaustive to train accurate analytical models, a selected subset of AEs takes part in a federated learning task wherein an E2E slice-level AE plays the role of an aggregation server.

Table I summarizes the features and the supervised output of the local datasets, which have been collected from a live LTE-Advanced (LTE-A) RAN with the hourly traffics of the top-10 over-the-top (OTT) applications. These accumulated realistic datasets are non-IID due to the different traffic profiles induced by the heterogeneous users' distribution and channel conditions. Such non-IIDness nature of datasets makes FL algorithms challenging for training.

Table I: Dataset Features and Output

Feature	Description
OTT Traffics	Apple, Facebook, Instagram, Netflix
CQI	Channel quality indicator
MIMO Full-Rank	MIMO full-rank usage (%)
# Users	Downlink Average active users
Output	Description
CPU Load	CPU resource consumption (%)

III. SLA VIOLATION-AWARE FEDERATED LEARNING WITH DYNAMIC LEARNING RATE ADAPTATION

An SLA is established between slice n tenant and the infrastructure provider so that any assigned resource to the tenant should not exceed a range $[\alpha_n, \beta_n]$ with a probability higher than an agreed threshold γ_n . This corresponds to solving a statistically constrained local resource allocation problem with both empirical cumulative density function (ECDF) and complementary ECDF (ECCDF) constraints at FL round t ($t = 0, \dots, T - 1$), i.e.,

$$\min_{\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}} \frac{1}{D_{k,n}} \sum_{i=1}^{D_{k,n}} \ell \left(y_{k,n}^{(i)}, \hat{y}_{k,n}^{(i)} \left(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_{k,n}^{(i)} \right) \right), \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } F_{\mathbf{x}_{k,n} \sim \mathcal{D}_{k,n}}(\alpha_n) = \frac{1}{D_{k,n}} \sum_{i=1}^{D_{k,n}} \mathbb{1} \left(\hat{y}_{k,n}^{(i)} < \alpha_n \right) \leq \gamma_n, \quad (1b)$$

$$\tilde{F}_{\mathbf{x}_{k,n} \sim \mathcal{D}_{k,n}}(\beta_n) = \frac{1}{D_{k,n}} \sum_{i=1}^{D_{k,n}} \mathbb{1} \left(\hat{y}_{k,n}^{(i)} > \beta_n \right) \leq \gamma_n, \quad (1c)$$

which is solved by invoking the so-called *proxy Lagrangian* framework [12]. This consists first on considering two Lagrangians as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}} &= \frac{1}{D_{k,n}} \sum_{i=1}^{D_{k,n}} \ell \left(y_{k,n}^{(i)}, \hat{y}_{k,n}^{(i)} \left(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_{k,n}^{(i)} \right) \right) \\ &+ \lambda_1 \Psi_1 \left(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)} \right) + \lambda_2 \Psi_2 \left(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\lambda} = \lambda_1 \Phi_1 \left(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)} \right) + \lambda_2 \Phi_2 \left(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)} \right), \quad (2b)$$

where $\Phi_{1,2}$ and $\Psi_{1,2}$ represent the original constraints and their smooth surrogates, respectively. Specifically, the indicator terms in (1b) and (1c) are replaced with Logistic functions. This optimization task turns out to be a non-zero-sum two-player game in which the $\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}$ -player aims at minimizing $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}}$, while the λ -player wishes to maximize \mathcal{L}_λ [13, Lemma 8]. While optimizing the first Lagrangian w.r.t. $\mathbf{W}_{k,n}$ requires differentiating the constraint functions $\Psi_1(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)})$ and $\Psi_2(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)})$, to differentiate the second Lagrangian w.r.t. λ we only need to evaluate $\Phi_1(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)})$ and $\Phi_2(\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)})$. Hence, a surrogate is only necessary for the $\mathbf{W}_{k,n}$ -player; the λ -player can continue using the original constraint functions. Via Lagrange multipliers, the λ -player chooses how much to weigh the proxy constraint functions, but does so in such a way as to satisfy the original constraints, and ends up reaching a nearly-optimal nearly-feasible solution [14].

In addition, to improve convergence stability under non-IID conditions and reduce SLA violations, we incorporate a new *SLA-driven adaptive learning rate policy*. At every local epoch l , each AE (k, n) updates its learning rate $\eta_\lambda^{(l)}$ according to the observed SLA violation rate $\nu_{k,n}$, i.e.,

$$\eta_\lambda^{(l)} = \begin{cases} 0.01 \cdot \eta_\lambda, & \text{if } \nu_{k,n} > S_{th}, \\ 0.1 \cdot \eta_\lambda, & \text{if } \nu_{k,n} < S_{th}, \\ \eta_\lambda, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where S_{th} denotes the SLA violation threshold. This integration ensures that the optimization not only respects SLA constraints but also dynamically adapts the learning process to improve both efficiency and reliability in federated training.

IV. SLA-DRIVEN ADAPTIVE LEARNING RATE BASED STOCHASTIC FL POLICY

Our aim is to adjust the learning rate dynamically and also select only a subset of active AEs in each FL round to optimize the FL computation time and the underlying resource consumption. Here, we consider our previously proposed [10] SLA-driven stochastic AE selection policy. So, upon the completion of the training at round t , each AE (k, n) evaluates the generalization of its FL model using a typical test dataset \tilde{D}_n of size \tilde{D}_n that is common to all monitoring systems of slice n and calculates the so-called SLA violation rate as [10],

$$\nu_{k,n} = \frac{1}{\tilde{D}_n} \sum_{i=1}^{\tilde{D}_n} \mathbb{1} \left[\left(\hat{y}_{k,n}^{(i)} < \alpha_n \right) \cup \left(\hat{y}_{k,n}^{(i)} > \beta_n \right) \right]. \quad (4)$$

Next, at each FL round t , all of the participated AEs send their SLA violation rates to the server which generates a probability distribution using `softmax` function as,

$$\pi_{k,n} = \frac{\exp\{-\nu_{k,n}\}}{\sum_{p=1}^K \exp\{-\nu_{p,n}\}}, \quad (5)$$

Algorithm 1: SLA-Driven Adaptive Learning Rate Federated Learning Policy.

```

Input:  $K, m, \eta_\lambda, T, L$ . # See Table II
Input: Initial learning rate  $\eta_\lambda$ , SLA threshold  $S_{th}$ .
Output: Trained global model  $\mathbf{W}_n^{(T)}$ .
for  $t = 1, \dots, T$  do
  // -- SLA Violation Estimation --
  parallel for  $k = 1, \dots, K$  do
    Each AE( $k, n$ ) calculates SLA violation rate  $\nu_{k,n}$  according to
    the SLA violation policy and reports it to the server
  end parallel for
  // -- Probability Distribution for Client Selection --
  for  $k = 1, \dots, K$  do
     $\pi_{k,n} = \frac{\exp\{-\nu_{k,n}\}}{\sum_{l=1}^K \exp\{-\nu_{l,n}\}}$ 
  end
  Server initializes  $\mathbf{W}_n^{(0)}$  with initial parameters.
  // -- SLA-Driven Client Selection --
   $\text{AE}_{k_1,n}^{(t)}, \dots, \text{AE}_{k_m,n}^{(t)} \sim \{\pi_{1,n}, \dots, \pi_{K,n} \mid \text{AE}_{1,n}, \dots, \text{AE}_{K,n}\}$ 
  // -- Local Training with Adaptive Learning Rate --
  parallel for  $k \in \{k_1, \dots, k_m\}$  do
    for  $l = 0, \dots, L - 1$  do
       $\eta_\lambda \leftarrow \text{adapt\_learning\_rate}(\eta_\lambda, \nu_{k,n})$ ; // Update LR
      dynamically based on SLA violation rate
      Solve the proxy-Lagrangian game between  $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}}$  and  $\mathcal{L}_\lambda$ 
      using  $\eta_\lambda$ 
      Update local weights  $\mathbf{W}_{k,l}$ 
    end
  return  $\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)} = \mathbf{W}_{k,L-1}$ 
  Send  $\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}$  to the server. end parallel for
  // -- Aggregation --
   $\mathbf{W}_n^{(t+1)} = \sum_{k \in \{k_1, \dots, k_m\}} \frac{D_{k,n}}{D_n} \mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}$ 
  Server broadcasts  $\mathbf{W}_n^{(t+1)}$  to all  $K$  clients.
end

```

wherein AEs with low SLA violation are given a high probability of FL participation to drive the model convergence, but also AEs with high SLA violation might take part in the FL training with a low probability to guarantee the generalization that could stem from their datasets. Based on the probability distribution, only a subset of $m < K$ AEs is drawn at each FL round to,

$$\text{AE}_{k_1,n}^{(t)}, \dots, \text{AE}_{k_m,n}^{(t)} \sim \{\pi_{1,n}, \dots, \pi_{K,n} \mid \text{AE}_{1,n}, \dots, \text{AE}_{K,n}\}, \quad (6)$$

Thus, the AEs would have stochastically participated in the FL task while avoiding the concurrent training at each round. Moreover, during training, instead of using a fixed learning rate, each selected client dynamically adjusts its learning rate at every local epoch according to the adaptive SLA-driven policy, defined in equation 3. Each client then performs L local epochs with the updated learning rate, solving the proxy-Lagrangian game between the model loss $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}}$ and the constraint loss \mathcal{L}_λ . After training, each client returns its final weight $\mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)}$

to the server. The model averaging in the server at round t is performed as:

$$\mathbf{W}_n^{(t+1)} = \sum_{k \in \{k_1, \dots, k_m\}} \frac{D_{k,n}}{D_n} \mathbf{W}_{k,n}^{(t)} \quad (7)$$

Where D_n is the sum of datasets sizes over all slice n 's AEs. After that, the server broadcasts the updated global model to all clients. This process repeats until convergence, enabling SLA-compliant, adaptive, and efficient federated learning. The overall procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1.

V. KUBERNETES-BASED DEPLOYMENT OF FL SYSTEM

In this paper, we present a Kubernetes-based FL solution with real-time visualization capabilities to evaluate the feasibility of our algorithm in realistic scenarios and demonstrate the scalability of the proposed policy. Unlike preliminary implementation relying on Docker Compose [10], our approach directly leverages Kubernetes for container orchestration like [15], aligning with the principles of slice-enabled Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) environments defined in ETSI NFV IFA 029 [16]. Furthermore, the implementation resonates with ongoing efforts in ETSI ZSM [1] for zero-touch management paving the way for interoperable and standardized FL deployments in 5G and beyond.

A. Architecture

Fig. 2 depicts the architecture of the proposed SLA-driven FL system deployed on Kubernetes. The FL server (OSS server) and an orchestration module are co-located within a single pod, while multiple AEs, acting as FL clients, run concurrently as separate pods managed by Kubernetes network. To monitor the overall performance of the FL system, Prometheus collects the resulting performance metrics from the server, which are queried and visualized through Grafana dashboards deployed via Helm charts. The framework consists of two main components:

- **Server pods:** A FL server pod is deployed as a single Kubernetes `Deployment` that coordinates the FL process across all clients. The server pod runs `main.py`, which acts as the controller, and a `Server` class that implements the FL logic. It exposes two ports, one for client communication and another for monitoring. It provides REST-based interfaces for client registration (`POST/client`), client selection initiation (`GET/select-clients`), SLA data collection (`POST/SLA`), and reception of model updates (`PUT/model-weights`).
- **Client pods:** Multiple client pods are deployed as a `StatefulSet`, each acting as an Analytic Engine (AE) that performs local training and communicates with the server. Each client pod runs `app.py` for REST communication and a client module to implement the ML models for training. It exposes two REST endpoints to

start calculation and send SLA violation rates (`PUT/SLA`) and Trigger the local FL training (`POST/training`).

All communications occur over HTTP using REST interfaces. Kubernetes `Service` objects provide stable networking: a `ClusterIP` service exposes the server internally, while a `headless` service enables direct addressing of client pods through DNS.

B. Workflow of the Federated Learning Network

The FL workflow requires the server pod to be active and at least one client pod to be available. The process is as follows:

- **Registration:** Clients, deployed as a `StatefulSet`, register with the server (exposed via `ClusterIP`) through `POST/client`.
- **Client selection:** The server requests SLA reports (`Post/SLA`) from clients, derives a probability distribution using a softmax function, and selects participants via `np.random.choice`.
- **Training and aggregation:** Selected clients perform local training upon `POST /training`, adjusting their learning rate dynamically based on observed SLA violation rates to improve convergence stability. After training, each client sends updated model weights back to the server through `PUT /model-weights`, and then the server averages all model weights to update the global model.
- **Monitoring:** After each round, the server exposes performance evaluation metrics. Prometheus collects these, and Grafana dashboard (via Helm charts) provides real-time visualization.

This setup enables real-time tracking of federated training progress, resource utilization, and SLA compliance.

VI. RESULTS

A. Parameter Settings and Baseline

We consider below three primary slices to analyze the proposed FL policy, defined as follows:

- **eMBB:** Netflix, Youtube and Facebook Video,
- **Social Media:** Facebook, Whatsapp and Instagram,
- **Browsing:** Apple, HTTP and QUIC,

Here, the traffic associated with each mentioned slice is the sum of the underlying OTTs' traffics collected from the hourly traffics of the slices for five days. We use vectors α , β for the resource bounds, and γ for the thresholds corresponding to the different slices for a particular resource. The parameter settings are mentioned in Table II.

B. Performance Evaluation

For performance evaluation, we compare the proposed **ALR-FL** solution under two strategies – (i) with client selection (**w/CS**)(proposed one) and (ii) with all clients participating (**w/All**) across all network slices. In addition, for convergence

Figure 2: SLA-driven scalable FL deployments on Kubernetes with $S1 = 15$ and $S2 = 20$ FL Clients

Table II: Settings

Parameter	Description	Value
N	# Slices	3
K	# AEs	30 (Simul.), (15, 20) (Emul.)
m	# Selected AEs	15 (Simul.), 10 (Emul.)
$D_{k,n}$	Local dataset size	1000 samples
T	# Max FL rounds	50
L	# Local epochs	100
R_λ	Lagrange multiplier radius	Constrained: 10^{-5}
η_λ	Base Learning rate	0.02

analysis, we incorporate another baseline solution, namely the Static Learning Rate FL (**SLR-FL w/CS**), evaluated under the same network slices. The results of the performance evaluation are summarized as follows:

Convergence: Figure 3a demonstrates that the proposed ALR-FL w/cs outperforms the version using all clients (w/all), achieving faster convergence and lower Normalized MSE, especially for eMBB and Social Media traffic. Furthermore, we can observe from the Figure 3b that ALR-FL w/cs converges faster than the baseline model SLR-FL w/cs across all network slices. Finally, The proposed **ALR-FL** outperforms the baselines because it adaptively tunes the learning rate based on SLA feedback, ensuring stable convergence under heterogeneous and non-IID conditions. When combined with client selection strategy (**ALR-FL w/cs**), it further enhances efficiency by prioritizing clients with lower SLA violations, reducing overhead and improving accuracy compared to static (**SLR-FL**) and full-participation (**w/All**) approaches.

Table III: Convergence Time

Model (All slices)	Computation Time until convergence
ALR-FL w/cs	20s (15 FL rounds)
ALR-FL w/all	50s (17 FL rounds)

Computation Time and SLA Compliance: Tables III and IV show that the proposed ALR-FL w/cs policy outperforms

the w/all setting by reducing computation time and maintaining SLA violations below 0.01. The integration of SLA-aware client selection with the proposed adaptive learning rate policy reduces computation and communication overhead and also accelerates training, making it more efficient for resource-constrained environments.

Table IV: SLA violation rate

FL Model	eMBB	Social Media	Browsing
ALR-FL w/cs	0.0	0.0	0.003
ALR-FL w/all	0.0	0.0	0.01

Scalability and Performance Analysis on Kubernetes: Finally, we deployed the complete FL solution on the Kubernetes platform, as described in Section V. Here, we focus on eMBB network slices for CPU load prediction, considering 15 and 20 FL clients for evaluation, while 10 clients are selected in each FL round to participate in training according to the SLA-driven selection policy. As shown in Fig. 4 and Table V, the proposed system achieves fast convergence, maintains a low SLA violation rate (<0.01), and requires minimal computation time to reach the convergence point. These results show that selecting a subset of AEs maintains high performance as the number of AEs grows, confirming the proposed FL solution's scalability, efficiency, and strong SLA compliance.

Table V: Performance analysis

FL clients	Computation Time until convergence	SLA Violation Rates
$S1 = 15$	60s (15 FL rounds)	0.007
$S2 = 20$	80s (20 FL rounds)	0.002

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a scalable, cloud-native, SLA-driven FL framework deployed on Kubernetes, incorporating a proposed novel dynamic learning rate strategy with a stochastic client selection policy. By prioritizing AE based client pods based on their SLA violation rates and adaptively adjusting learning rates during local training, the framework

(a) ALR_FL

(b) SLR_FL

Figure 3: FL training MSE loss vs. number of FL rounds of the proposed policy for $m = 15$ and $K = 30$. SLA bound, with $\alpha = [0, 0, 0]$, $\beta = [6, 9, 10]$ % and $\gamma = [0.01, 0.01, 0.01]$ in constrained case (Simulated)

Figure 4: NMSE loss analysis on kubernetes with $S1 = 15$ and $S2 = 20$ FL Clients

stabilizes FL convergence, reduces training time, and minimizes both computational costs and SLA violations. Numerical results from simulated and cloud-native emulated scenarios demonstrate the effectiveness, efficiency, and scalability of the proposed policy. Future work will focus on deploying the framework in real multi-technology domain networks with relevant proof of concepts to validate its practical applicability.

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